

MORAL AND ETHICAL ASPECTS OF RESPONSIBILITY AND PERSONAL FREEDOM IN M. SHELLEY'S «FRANKENSTEIN»

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Abstract

The article examines M. Shelley's «Frankenstein» as an example of the so-called second wave of English gothic novel. M. Shelley's talent hides not only in the skill of an unexpected and horrifying plot but also in the depth of ethic problems touched. M. Shelley skillfully deals with the aspects of human's responsibility in the case of interfering with nature's processes. M. Shelley's creative method is a combination of romantic gothic trend and has many features of the Enlightenment philosophy.

The literary image created by M. Shelley was widely used in Masscult in which the character has nothing in common with the author's idea. The «creature» is typically introduced as a monster. When the character of a book begins living its own life, it separates from its creator (this aspect in this study is particularly relevant). Then the author's intention may be different from the same author's vision and interpretation.

Key words: gothic novel, ethic problems, responsibility, the nature of horror, the creator and his creature.

The problem raised in the article has always been important and topical as people always wanted to become demiurges, creators, to be just like gods. The first embodiment of this desire in literature was the mythical Pygmalion. However, the sculptor in that myth created only a marble shell. The origin of life was a mystery to the ancient Greeks, that only gods possessed, so they (gods) breathed life into the artist's creation. The theme of creation can be found in folk and literary tales. The pantheistic worldview and the sense of energy in each piece of nature determine that human imagination does not search for reasons why the creatures of snow, flour, wood, etc. come to life as if by themselves.

M. Shelley's work belongs to the so-called second wave of British writers who appeal to the nature of horror. M. Shelley's «Frankenstein» has undergone many editions, has been redefined and transformed into various art forms – first in the theater and then in the cinema. Popular mass culture has blended the images of the creator and his creation. That is why the name of a young scientist Victor Frankenstein is usually given to a nameless creature that was born in a laboratory. The name of the scientist in the novel by M. Shelley is always identified with his creation, and the word «Frankenstein» has become a common name that is used to denote a brutal monster, the very existence of which contradicts the laws of nature, and whose actions are aimed to make harm to humans. This problem may also be interpreted as a problem of personality split because the creature in M. Shelley's novel is sometimes called «the monstrous projection» (Yampol'sky, 1996.) of its creator. The creature has no name. Throughout the narration the author calls him «a creature», «a poor thing», «a ghost», «a monster» or «a demon». But this creature has grown beyond the borders of a literary experiment. It would be interesting to refer to the problem of spirituality of this artificially made body. The nameless character possesses inherent ability for feelings, compassion, desire to help, the need for human society – all those components of a human being are moved and forced by some immaterial energy. And the aspect of spiritual problems needs proper skills of theological analysis.

A young writer (she was only 19 years old) laid out to write a book that would «address hidden fears and cause shudder; make the reader be afraid to look back, would thump heart and ripe blood in the veins» (Shelley, 1992). Mary won the contest and her opponents noted the writer's talent and the uniqueness of her work. However, understanding her marginal status, in the preface to the novel, M. Shelley wrote that she was not obliged to the husband in any episode or thought.

The main character of M. Shelley's novel traces the way to knowledge that is not limited by certain ethical considerations but this process results in monster creating. But rather quickly he understood that this track was wrong. And the creature was already there against his will. At the same time he/it (the creature) was trying to understand the world and himself, his own place in the world, and rightly blamed Victor

in the lack of responsibility for his existence. Frankenstein and his creature is a Gnostic pair illustrating the futility of human attempts to take over the functions of God and the impossibility of knowing God. By analyzing this situation through the Enlightenment rationality prism it turns it into a problem of moral responsibility of scientists for their own deeds.

The creative method of M. Shelley is the synthesis of romantic and gothic reference to the nature of human fear and moral and philosophical tenets of the Enlightenment. The last aspect as well deals with the problem of human happiness. The writer feels not only fear of the very process of creation and abuse of the nature's laws but sympathizes with the lonely miserable creature. Like Robinson who felt lonely and taught parrots to talk just to hear at least this simulation of human language, so the «child» of Frankenstein learned to speak and did it very quickly.

This character is a human creature as he is able to feel. When his father and creator rejects him, this miserable monster still does not understand but can feel and at the same time shows self-criticism. «I was miserable, helpless and unhappy, – he told Victor about the early days of his «life», – I did not understand and did not know what to do. I just felt that I was suffering, – and cried» (Shelley, 1992). The demon is fairly described as a very attentive one; the nameless character evolves in his own abilities and worldview, with his mind and soul he understands his place in the Universe: «I began to recognize the stream that consumed me, and the trees that covered me with the shadow. I realized that pleasant sounds I heard were created by tiny winged beings. I had to learn to express feelings that agitated me, and wild sounds that I uttered, I was scared» (Shelley, 1992).

The monster has enormous potential. That's a true superhuman: he is as tall as the giants that inhabited the planet of the legendary Golden Age, this creature has extraordinary physical strength, can stand cold and heat, is resistant to hunger and fatigue. Watching the residents of the slum from his ambush, the creature quickly learns to distinguish people by age and sex, makes conclusions about their options, feels joy and pain.

The «new Adam» that was born in the laboratory is more holistic and organic than ordinary people. Being created of the pieces of human bodies, he/it is free from their (people's) born sin. His/its extremely strong body does not even need to eat meat

of dead animals and feeds on berries, nuts and roots instead, this creature is an integral part of nature, as follows humanitarian principles of peaceful coexistence with all living things and the surroundings. The soul that lives in an ugly body is clean and open. The creature has no memory so looks at the world as a naive newborn baby.

The scientist undertakes to God, creating a new being. The creation of Victor Frankenstein raises the question of the liability of his creator to him. He says that no one is allowed to play with life: «Even you, my creator – the creature desperately exclaims, – hate and push me, your creation, away. And you'd like to kill me. How can you play with life?» (Shelley, 1992). The postulate of A. de Saint-Exupery's novel turns into the inverse proportionality in M. Shelley's novel: «You are my creator, and I'm your host» (Shelley, 1992) – that's a real challenge to the researcher from his child. These words embody the aspect of parental responsibility to children and the fatalistic penalty for interference with God's deals.

The real cause of the tragic ending according to M. Shelley is that the human world is a prisoner of stereotypes. As we know the work under consideration was a successful literary experiment. The idea of the novel was born at night, when a monstrous creature appeared in front of the inner vision of the writer. In the preface to the work, she wrote what was the most scarring for her: «What could be worse for the people than any attempts to emulate the unique creation of God?» (Shelley, 1992).

The author shares the feelings of the creator, she feels what he feels and is as much scared as he is. In the preface she puts a rhetorical question of «what could be worse for the people than any attempts to emulate the unique creation of God». And then with the character of hers expresses the hope that «the spark of life would fade when the creature was abandoned to its own fate» (Shelley, 1992). M. Shelley supposed her readers would be as scared as she was: «What scared me would make the others shudder, it's enough only to describe the ghost which visited me at night» (Shelley, 1992). Although the creation of a scientist is called the «demon» and the «ugly one», it is not left without the author's love and compassion. «So I send my ugly offspring into the world, – M. Shelley writes in the preface to «Frankenstein» (is it told about the novel or a nameless character?). – I feel tenderness towards it, because it was born in that happy time when death and grief were just words to me» (Shelley, 1992).

The essence of horror in the novel by M. Shelley differs from that aspect of the early Gothic novels. This difference is even proclaimed by the main character. He admits that he has never experienced any fear of darkness, and a cemetery seemed to him only as «a resting place for dead bodies» (Shelley, 1992). Thus, with scientific progress, Victor Frankenstein makes him similar to Prometheus who was bearing fire to warm and illuminate human life. Full of pride the character exclaims: «I was the first who destined to overcome the boundaries between life and death and illuminate our dark world by dazzling light» (Shelley, 1992). Excited with his success the scientist begins to make plans to change the laws of nature: «Once I learned how to revive a dead matter after a while I'll be able to give a second life to flesh which death has doomed to extinction» (Shelley, 1992).

The problem of the creator's responsibility towards his creation and the world that has to accept this creation is solved dramatically. It should be emphasized that M. Shelley's talent which does not only appeal to both interesting and terrible story, but also reveals to the depth and ambiguity of moral and ethical issues. The novel makes the readers shudder with fear in front of artificially made creature neither dead and nor alive, makes tremble with horror because of human cruelty; the work evokes sympathy towards the pseudo-scholar who desired to become Prometheus but instead became a necromancer that played with death and as well we regret his unfortunate creation which sought to achieve harmony for his own soul and to bring harmony in the cruel world of the living.

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